

The Effects of Theoretical Concepts in Managerial Economics on the Individual's Psychological Decision Making and Implementation Process

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Niyaz Bokvadze

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EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 |
RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS:**

ASI@EUROPE.DE

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Author(s) Name Surname:

İlknur GENÇOĞLU YILDIRIM

University:

Northwest University

Department: Psychology

Title: Doctor

Date: 13.08.2023

Abstract

When analyzing the interplay between decision-making processes in psychology and theoretical concepts in managerial economics within a comprehensive framework, it has been noted that these concepts exert a significant influence on the decision-making process and have a notable impact on the psychological decision-making processes of individuals.

In contemporary marketplaces, where the decision-making process has significant importance, the chosen subject for study is insurance as a model product. All research conducted in this article will focus only on insurance products. The occurrence of many challenges in the implementation of decision-making processes within the insurance industry is an unavoidable reality. Utilizing theoretical principles proves to be a viable approach in addressing unexpected challenges.

Constraint

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Limited to literature review.

Notifications

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Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

When analyzing the interplay between decision-making processes in psychology and theoretical concepts in managerial economics within a comprehensive framework, empirical evidence suggests a significant impact of these concepts on the decision-making process. Moreover, these concepts exert a notable influence on the psychological decision-making processes of individuals.

In contemporary marketplaces, characterized by the utmost significance of the decision-making process, the selected product for examination was identified as insurance for the purposes of this research paper. The whole of the research conducted in this article will be focused only on insurance products. The use of decision making in the insurance business is prone to encountering a multitude of challenges. Utilizing theoretical principles is a viable approach for addressing encountered challenges.

Research findings indicate that business and management entities gain a competitive advantage by integrating theoretical ideas into their operations, aligning them with individual requirements, and therefore creating a more favorable market environment. It has been shown that they demonstrate enhanced performance and achieve more achievement via the use of this approach.

The conducted investigations involving the analyzed insurance firms have yielded facts that strongly corroborate our theoretical framework. Based on the available data, it has been noticed that the use of theoretical ideas yields favorable outcomes in the marketplaces, enabling insurance businesses and managers to effectively compete with their counterparts and enhance their internal SWOT analysis.

The effectiveness of theoretical concepts in managerial economics has been observed in facilitating effective communication between the insurance sector and its customers. These concepts also contribute to enhancing the decision-making and implementation processes within the business and management unit. Furthermore, the theoretical concepts play a significant role in conducting SWOT analysis of enterprises and making strategic decisions by evaluating internal elements of business activities. Research findings have shown the efficacy of this approach in facilitating progress and development. Furthermore, empirical observations have indicated that it yields positive outcomes in the decision-making and implementation processes, demonstrating a satisfactory degree of effectiveness.

The findings of our thesis study indicate that enterprises that actively incorporate theoretical concepts from managerial economics into their decision-making and implementation processes within the business and management unit tend to achieve greater success compared to enterprises that do not actively utilize these concepts.

Keywords: *Decision Making Process in Psychology, Making Process, Psychology and Economics Concepts, Psychology and Theoretical Economics Concepts*

Introduction

When considering the theoretical concepts in managerial economics within the context of the psychological decision-making process, it is evident that these concepts have a significant impact on the decision-making process and the psychological decision-making of individuals.

In contemporary marketplaces, where the psychological aspect of buying a product has significant importance, the selection of product insurance is regarded as a subject of investigation in scholarly articles. The whole of the research conducted in this article will focus only on insurance products.

Insurance may be seen as a mechanism for transferring risk. According to the TSRSB (2010), Customers make several selections when they choose to get plans and automotive insurance from diverse insurance firms, with the aim of fulfilling their wants and aspirations. These selections might be seen as a means of resolving the issues faced by customers.

The establishment of production objectives and sales organization within an insurance firm may be achieved by the allocation of varying weights to different branches, such as insurance, traffic, fire, earthquake, engineering, personal injury, transportation, agricultural, liability, and others. The determination of which branch the firm will prioritize is an outcome of a decision-making process influenced by several variables. The criteria include several elements, including market demand, competition, agency and direct sales structure, firm capital, branch profitability potential, prospective production, and management profitability/growth plan. According to Yalçın (2010),

The centralization of psychological decision-making processes has coincided with the growing use of mass communication technology. The current scenario has acquired a professional aspect via the facilitation of insurance industry growth.

Upon closer examination of the various decision-making processes undertaken by customers, it becomes evident that prior experience does not always warrant the inclusion of further information. The consumer exhibits established purchasing patterns and engaged in brand loyalty with little cognitive effort. The concept of brand loyalty is of primary importance. Customers have a direct role in the execution of the purchasing process within a company context. They exhibit a preference for brokers who provide lesser costs.

The attitudes and actions shown by customers towards a service with which they have prior experience are influenced by specified selection criteria and result in reduced time requirements. The service class is discussed, but no details on the agency are provided. The likelihood of receiving support from a previously engaged agency is considerable, yet the emergence of novel circumstances may necessitate engaging other agencies. Additionally, it is possible to get information on alternative services. Psychological decision-making behavior

may be shown once again in the context of satisfaction. If there is a state of discontent, the agent is replaced.

The service choice process encompasses many stages, including knowledge of the issue, identification of options, assessment of alternatives, making the purchase decision and buying, and experiencing post-purchase emotions.

The primary target demographic for our study comprises individuals employed by agencies operating inside the Republic of Turkey.

The judgments made by Insurance Agencies, which present challenges to social life, have significant relevance in relation to the novelty of the study. This research will make a valuable contribution to the existing literature since it will be the first of its kind to investigate managers linked with the insurance industry.

It is well acknowledged that the Turkish Travel Agencies Association (TÜRSAB) has a network of roughly 5,500 agencies inside the Republic of Turkey. The research will include selecting a sample of managers from the agencies under study. The study will focus on examining the impact of predetermined variables on the decision-making challenges experienced by these managers, and how these challenges affect their service behavior.

Based on the analysis of many studies, it has been shown that the decision-making and implementation process in managerial economics yields significant influence and advantages. In this scenario, it is assessed that those who possess advanced psychological decision-making and execution abilities exhibit a higher degree of activity compared to those without such skills.

It is acknowledged that the absence of theoretical notions in our study leads to poor outcomes, since decisions are made only based on client pleasure without proper consideration. This study aims to investigate the incorporation of theoretical ideas in insurance firms, specifically focusing on the hitherto unexplored sub-topic of "decision making and implementation" in relation to corporate success. In this instance, both parties place significant emphasis on the widespread adoption of the Gary S. Becker model and remain steadfast in preserving the model's uniqueness. According to Bilen (2008),

The prevailing consensus among scholars is that firms generally do not prioritize theoretical notions as the primary determinant of their decision-making processes.

As the body of research in this topic expanded, the investigations initially conducted only on the absence of theoretical frameworks in the early stages have evolved to include other aspects, including the significance and severity of indecisiveness. The research has shown that these theoretical psychological choices constitute a significant determinant.

Our study will contribute to the existing body of literature by focusing on the examination of the potential of insurance businesses in Turkey. The subject of theoretical notions in Insurance Companies has not been previously explored till the undertaking of our research. Companies often disregard theoretical principles. This study will add to the existing literature by introducing theoretical notions that have not been previously explored.

Previous research has highlighted the need of incorporating theoretical ideas in corporate practices. However, there seems to be a dearth of studies focusing on crucial aspects such as business, advertising, Consumer Rights, agency, and pricing inside organizations. The study is anticipated to serve as a valuable reference for firms, providing insights into the application of theoretical ideas and the use of elements that influence consumer happiness in the future.

To develop a robust insurance company management model, it is imperative for leaders to actively engage in organizational structuring, oversee managerial activities to establish a coherent theoretical framework, promptly acknowledge and commend managerial achievements, and effectively address the needs and demands of both managers and customers within the organization, while also considering the requests and challenges posed by competing companies in the market. In order to foster a culture of continuous improvement and ensure the widespread adoption of total quality, it is imperative for managers to exhibit openness to new ideas, promote productivity, actively engage in improvement studies, authorize work, and provide resources and assistance. Furthermore, managers should actively participate not only within the organization but also in external interactions with customers, thereby assuming an active role in establishing and maintaining relationships.

Methodology

This study aims to analyze the impact of theoretical ideas in managerial economics on the decision-making and execution processes inside business and management units.

The primary objective of the thesis proposal is to conduct a thorough analysis of managerial economics, investigate the underlying psychological decision-making processes, explore the implementation strategies employed by enterprises, and effectively translate theoretical concepts into practical outcomes.

1. What is the impact of theoretical ideas in managerial economics on the decision-making process of businesses and management units from the perspective of customer behavior?
2. What is the impact of using theoretical principles in managerial economics throughout the implementation process of the business and management unit on the buying power of consumers?
3. What is the correlation between the theoretical principles in managerial economics and the decision-making and execution process of the company and management unit, considering the demographic features of the consumer?

In contemporary marketplaces, characterized by the prominence of the Managerial Economy, customers are increasingly encountering a growing array of items daily. Psychological and sociological elements, including education level, culture, attitudes, and behaviors, have been shown to have a significant influence on consumer purchasing decisions. However, it is important to note that other factors, such as product characteristics, pricing, advertising, and product addiction, all play a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior and influencing buy choices.

In contemporary marketplaces, firms place significant emphasis on their strategic choices aimed at differentiating their goods from competitors, drawing upon the theoretical constructs within the field of management economics. Business enterprises are engaged in a competitive endeavor within the market, using a combination of product attributes and various marketing strategies in order to get a competitive edge over rival firms. During this process, the company provides a customer application that facilitates the purchasing of their items, so promoting product dependency. Business enterprises strive to cultivate customer loyalty by encouraging repeated purchases, so ensuring that their goods are consistently chosen above competing alternatives.

Due to this rationale, enterprises carefully evaluate the benefits that may be derived from fostering product addiction, allocate substantial resources towards this objective, and strategically formulate and execute psychological strategies. When the marketing elements of a product align with customer expectations and result in repeat purchases, it may be inferred that the consumer is content with the product.

A method refers to the systematic series of procedures that are undertaken in order to arrive at a conclusion about a certain problem or issue. The research methodology encompasses the systematic gathering, examination, and interpretation of data that is essential for addressing the study topic at hand.

The research study conducted by Durmaz, Bahar, and Kurtlar (2011) used the 'Questionnaire Method' as a means of gathering and analyzing objective data directly from the source. In order to examine the effectiveness of theoretical ideas used by Insurance Companies in Turkey, the survey approach was employed. The questionnaire consists of statements that have been formulated based on the Likert scale. The study conducted by Elciz and Köker (2011) used a seven-point Likert scale to assess the elements that influence the theoretical ideas outlined in the scale.

Furthermore, within the scope of the surveys, Insurance Companies were requested to document the challenges they often face in relation to theoretical ideas and the adverse consequences they experience when failing to use those concepts. The primary objective of include this question in the survey is to determine if Insurance Companies demonstrate the potential of the firm while using theoretical notions.

Rationale of the Study

The market for consumer goods is characterized by a psychological battle to influence individuals' decision-making processes and product adoption. The dominant firms in this conflict are on the verge of unveiling new subcultures and forms of affiliation. The impact of brands on customer behavior throughout the purchase decision-making process has emerged as a significant area of study in contemporary times.

The effectiveness of theoretical concepts in managerial economics has been observed in facilitating accurate communication with consumers. The utilization of these concepts enhances

the psychological decision-making and implementation processes within the business and management unit. The significance of theoretical concepts lies in their contribution to strategic decision-making, particularly in the measurement of internal factors and the improvement and development of business activities. It has been determined to be efficacious.

The business and management units demonstrate a commendable degree of use of theoretical principles in managing economics throughout the process of psychological decision making and execution.

In contemporary competitive environments, the significance of Information Technologies has seen a substantial rise, alongside the significance of novel goods and services. The ability to establish suitable and lucrative pricing strategies, tailored to certain regions and consumer segments, has become a must.

The acquisition and interpretation of information is contingent upon the use of technology.

The current advancements in technology are of a groundbreaking kind. Undoubtedly, the impact of information technology on the nation's economy, perception of productivity, and social dynamics has been substantial, giving rise to several transformative developments. Currently, there is a significant escalation in the impact of the internet on enterprises operating within the information and communication sector.

The Internet and technology-based information systems have a significant impact on several aspects of human interaction, including communication, information sharing, learning, and commercial operations. These platforms actively contribute to the reconfiguration of the economy and everyday routines.

The integration of internet technology and many business scenarios has become more interconnected in contemporary corporate operations. In the contemporary business landscape, it has become imperative for enterprises to incorporate the many possibilities presented by the internet into their operational framework. The integration of the Internet into everyday activities has led to advancements in the field of electronic commerce. The financial services industry has seen the most substantial transformation as a result of e-commerce, which has brought about considerable changes across several industries.

The insurance industry has just recently started developing electronic commerce applications in comparison to other intermediaries in the financial sector. In recent years, several insurance firms in the United States, Europe, and our nation have been advertising and marketing their goods and services using online platforms. The findings derived from the analyses and assessments conducted within the realm of internet insurance indicate a significant potential for fast growth in the domain of virtual insurance.

Given the rapid advancements in technology, it is anticipated that our nation will see a phase whereby the insurance industry may transcend its conventional framework and align itself with technical and commercial innovations. The burgeoning insurance industry in Turkey must comprehend the competitive enterprises that impact electronic commerce and assess the potential benefits and risks that arise from the utilization of commercial internet.

Findings

The primary sample population for this study comprises institutions in Turkey that engage in marketing activities on behalf of Insurance Agencies. These institutions develop personalized connections with consumers and aim to safeguard the well-being and assets of people.

The use of theoretical ideas at an advanced level by Insurance Companies has been identified as a significant aspect of research, contributing to the enhancement of customer satisfaction. Nevertheless, it is essential to restrict the demographic that will be included in the survey based on the practicality of the study.

However, it is important to acknowledge that the limitations of this study may raise concerns about the reproducibility of the obtained results. To ensure generalizability, the sample size was maintained at a predetermined level within the statistical framework. To facilitate the data collection process, efforts were made to guarantee that the sample population was drawn from the geographical region in where the author resides.

Economic development and the insurance business are seeing advancements in both developed and emerging nations. The insurance industry in Turkey has been capitalizing on the robust economic performance of the nation and shown notable expansion in recent times.

Based on the statistics provided by the Undersecretariat of Treasury, the proportion of premium production within the Turkish insurance sector's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has a rising trajectory. The proportion of total premiums in GDP experienced a rise from 1.40% to 1.55% in the year 2013. This upward trend has a favorable impact on shaping expectations. The insurance and private pension market in Turkey has substantial potential for expansion.

Alexander H. Church and Leon P. Alford: Principles of Management

In a 1912 article, Alexander Hamilton Church (1866-1936), a consultant specializing in cost systems, and Leon Pratt Alford (1877-1942), an electrical engineer, writer, and educator, put forward the contention that the area of management did not possess the essential attributes of a bona fide scientific study.

According to the authors, several strategies were suggested to tackle management challenges; however, their scientific validity was constrained by reliance on subjective perspectives. Moreover, the acceptance of these ideas was mostly shaped by the reputation and prestige of the persons promoting them, rather than a thorough evaluation of their logical merits. Church and Alford (year) argued that the progression of management from an art to a science necessitates the establishment of certain principles. The authors proposed two principles: (1) the methodical application of past experiences, and (2) the economic management of workforce, in addition to (3) the improvement of individual efficiency.

The concept of "experience," as defined by the authors, denotes the understanding and familiarity acquired via past occurrences. The authors advocate for doing a comprehensive examination of the given job, considering current documentation and performance metrics. Experiences possess intrinsic worth and play a crucial role in nurturing and perpetuating ancient customs and practices. Hence, it is essential that individuals assimilate all types of experiences inside their cognitive faculties before applying them in practical contexts, and new experiences need to stimulate the creation of inventive approaches for implementation.

Church and Alford (year) emphasized the importance of the concept of "labor" in their research. Labor is defined as the experiencing component of activities. The authors assert in their second principle that a significant portion of the current management discourse is centered on the inquiry into the appropriate handling of labor and the extent to which managerial control is deemed essential. In order to develop a well-organized community of activities, it is essential

to exert economic control over labor. Control is achieved using three unique processes, namely coordination, vision, and protection.

Argument

The contraction seen in the automotive sector during the year 2014 resulted in a highly competitive landscape within the vehicle insurance sector. The insurance business, along with other industries, saw significant impact from the swift surge in foreign currency during the first period of the year. The scenario was manifested by a rise in the number of loss items recorded in the financial statements of the organization.

Based on the Consumer Price Index, the insurance industry saw a growth rate in 2014 that was lower than the annual inflation rate of 8.17%. The significant contraction of these two locomotive branches within the sector, in response to inflation, had a crucial role in shaping the industry's outcomes in 2014. The primary contributor to this decline may be attributed to the reduction in sales of new vehicles as a result of the recession seen within the automobile industry.

Research Strategy

The novelty of the study topic, as shown by the absence of prior investigations in the existing literature, has significant implications for the trajectory and outcomes of the investigation. The effect of prior research on subsequent studies within the same topic area suggests that the introduction of novel subject matter in fresh research endeavors contributes to the cultivation of originality in scholarly investigations.

The primary rationale for the limited use of theoretical ideas in contemporary contexts is to provide guidance in accordance with prevailing circumstances, rather than serving as a basis for decision-making. The fundamental premise underlying all theoretical notions in a global context is the enhancement of organizational performance. In the scope of our study, we shall examine theoretical constructs pertaining to insurance businesses as a subsidiary factor. In this study, we will focus on the examination of elements that contribute to organizational change, creativity, psychological decision-making, and implementation processes, rather than relying just on theoretical notions.

In contemporary competitive environments, the significance of Information Technologies has seen a substantial rise, alongside the prominence of novel goods and services. The ability to establish suitable and lucrative pricing strategies, tailored to certain regions and consumer segments, has become a must.

The acquisition and interpretation of information is contingent upon the use of technology.

The current advancements in technology are of a revolutionary kind. Undoubtedly, the impact of information technology on the nation's economy, perception of productivity, and social dynamics has been substantial, giving rise to several transformative developments. Currently, there is a significant escalation in the impact of the internet on enterprises operating in the information and communication sector. The Internet and technological information systems have a significant impact on several aspects of human interaction, including communication, information sharing, learning, and commercial operations. These technologies actively contribute to the reconfiguration of the economy and everyday routines.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of many studies, it has been shown that the decision-making and implementation process in the field of management economics yields significant influence and advantages. This scenario is assessed based on an individual's proficiency in using psychological decision-making and execution abilities at an advanced level, indicating a higher degree of engagement compared to those without such talents.

In this setting, it is essential to place significant emphasis and value on the decision-making and execution abilities of the firm within the realm of managerial economics. It is important to disseminate knowledge on the psychological aspects of decision-making and the implementation process of managerial economics to both businesses and consumers via many channels.

There is a need for increased allocation of time towards the psychological decision-making and execution process, as well as the structure of activities and institutions to enhance efficiency. This is particularly important in the context of promoting music education among school students.

It is important to do a more extensive investigation into the proposed thesis topic, and these research efforts should be supplemented by postgraduate study.

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